

Frequency distribution of the F_3 population of the cross between Pankaj (P_1) and O.C. 1393 (P_2) among seedling heights.

parents were submerged in water maintained between 45 and 50 cm. After 12 days, 67.4% of the O.C. 1393, 34.1% of the progeny lines, and 27.0% of the Pankaj plants survived.

The increase in height (i.e. elongation ability) of the survivors averaged 66.2 cm for the F_3 lines, 73.2 cm for O.C. 1393, and 45.5 cm for Pankaj.

Thus, Pankaj as a parent in a lowland crossing program may produce desired intermediate plant height with good tolerance for submergence. ■

Contribution of tillers produced at different weeks to panicle formation

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The potential contribution to panicle formation of tillers produced in different weeks was investigated during the wet season. The short-duration variety Chandina and the medium-duration variety IR8 were grown in pots to avoid mutual shading.

Seedlings of both varieties started

Productive tillers and other yield components of Chandina and IR8 (av of 10 replications).

Variety	Tillers	Productive tiller (%)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Wt/panicle (g)	100-grain wt (g)	Contribution to total panicle wt (%)
Chandina	Primary	100	22	133	1.70	2.19	6
	2d wk	100	21	114	1.50	2.18	12
	3d wk	94	22	117	1.40	2.18	42
	4th wk	13	20	81	0.90	2.10	31
	5th wk	34	18	64	0.70	1.88	8
IR8	Primary	100	23	124	2.00	2.37	10
	2d wk	85	23	114	2.00	2.36	18
	3d wk	93	22	100	1.60	2.28	37
	4th wk	70	21	85	1.30	2.32	30
	5th wk	15	18	57	0.60	1.80	3

producing tillers the second week after sowing. The tillers produced each week until the 7th week after sowing were marked with wire rings.

In both varieties tillers produced within the third week were 93 to 100% productive and those produced in the fourth week 70 to 73% productive. Tillers produced in the 5th week were only 15% (IR8) and 34% (Chandina) productive (see table). None of the tillers produced during the 6th and 7th week developed panicles.

The panicle length, number of spikelets per panicle, and weight per

panicle were the highest in the primary panicle and decreased in subsequent panicles. However, the highest contribution to the total panicle weight was from panicles produced by the 3d- and 4th-week tillers. The 100-grain weight did not vary much among the panicles; however, it was extremely low in the panicles from 5th-week tillers.

A rice plant, whether of short or medium duration, has the potential to produce panicles from 5th-week tillers during the wet season. Such panicles contribute little, however, to the total panicle weight of a plant. ■

Tillering pattern of dwarf indica rice and its contribution to grain yield

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The growth and development of tillers — the prime units of grain production — directly affect the economic and total biological yields. Because basic research on tillering patterns is meager, the present study was undertaken on Cauvery cultivar, an early maturing semidwarf indica rice.

Primary tillers flowered earliest, followed by secondary and tertiary tillers

(see table). Growth parameters, such as plant height and number of rachillae per panicle, were higher in primary tillers. Leaf emergence was rapid and relative growth rate high in the mother culm and primary tillers. Early tillers originating at the same time had better vascular connections with the mother shoot. The diameter of internodes in tertiary tillers that emerged early was nearly double that of later internodes. Because of a large source for carbon assimilation (green leaves) and more sink capacity for accumulating photosynthates (panicles), the primary tillers contributed nearly half of the

Growth parameters and tillering pattern of Cauvery, a semidwarf indica rice, Varanasi, India.

Designation of tiller	Flowering days (no.) from germination	Ht (cm)	Bearing tillers (%)	Rachillae (no./pmick)	Yield contribution (%)
Mother culm	74	102.1	100	115.0	10
Primary bearing	76	99.3	95	103.2	50
Secondary bearing	77	94.5	71	101.7	35
Tertiary bearing	80	93.2	48	98.3	5

dry matter toward grain yield.

Tertiary tillers that emerged late were partially developed, and mostly unproductive, and their mortality was

high. Their vascular connections with the vascular elements of the main culm were poor. Because they are unsuccessful in the intraplant competition for

photosynthate and other growth requirements, they contribute less to grain yield. ■

Rice research priorities in Brazil

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Brazil is the largest rice producer and consumer in the western hemisphere. About 5 million ha have been cultivated

annually in the last 5 years. In 1977, 8.9 million t of rice was produced and annual per capita consumption rose to 45 kg. About 80% of Brazilian rice is grown in the uplands where seasonal distribution of rainfall causes wide yield fluctuations. Average yields are about 1.5 t/ha in upland areas and 3.7 t/ha on

irrigated land. Nearly all the 17 Brazilian states are involved in rice production, but 8 states produce 92%. The biggest upland rice-producing area is in the west central *Cerrado-Savanna* region. The production in this region, which has some 3.5 million ha of rice land, is sometimes more important than

Rice research priorities, Brazil, 1977.

Discipline	Priority level by state ^a																
	RS	SC	PR	SP	RJ	ES	MG	GO	DF	MS	SE	AL	PI	MA	RO	AM	PA
• Crop breeding, genetics, and physiology																	
Disease resistance	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	—	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Insect resistance	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	—	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Threshing resistance	—	—	—	1*	—	—	1*	1*	—	1*	—	—	1	1	—	—	—
Lodging resistance	—	—	1	1	—	—	1	1	—	1	—	—	—	—	1	—	—
Drought resistance	—	—	1*	—	1*	—	1*	1*	1*	1*	—	—	—	—	1*	—	—
Low temperature tolerance	1	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Poor soils tolerance	—	2*	1*	1*	—	—	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	—	—
Agronomic traits	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2
• Crop protection																	
Management and control of weeds	1	3	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	1
Survey and control of pests	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	2
Survey and control of diseases	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1
• Cropping system																	
Companion crop	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2	1	3	—	—
Rotation	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	—	—	2	2	2	1	1
Ecological adaptability	—	—	1	1	—	—	1	1	1	1	—	—	2	2	2	1	1
Cultural practices	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	2
Economic viability of the systems	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2
• Soil and water management and conservation																	
Relation soil-water-plant	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1
Irrigation methods	1	—	1	1	—	—	1	1	1	1	2	2	3	2	2	1	1
Drainage methods	1	1	—	—	1	1	—	—	—	—	2	2	—	3	—	1	1
Mineral nutrition	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3
Fertility	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Erosion control	—	—	3	3	—	—	3	3	3	3	—	—	3	3	3	—	—
• Autoecology																	
Climatic conditions	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	3	2	2	2	2
Ecophysiology	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	3	3
• Seed production and technology																	
Production and seed analysis	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
Transportation and storage	2	3	3	3	—	—	3	2	—	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Processing and storage	3	—	3	3	—	—	3	3	—	3	—	—	—	—	—	2	2
Seed quality	1	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	—	—	—	3	3	—	—
• Design of farm machinery and agricultural mechanization																	
Cultivation equipment	1	—	2	1	2	2	2	2	—	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Processing equipment	1	—	2	1	2	2	2	2	—	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

^aRS = Rio Grande Do Sul, SC = Santa Catarina, PR = Parana, SP = Sao Paulo, RJ = Rio de Janeiro, ES = Espirito Santo, MG = Minas Gerais, GO = Goias, DF = Distrito Federal, MS = Masso Grosso Do Sul, SE = Sergipe, AL = Alagoas, PI = Piaui, MA = Maranhao, RO = Rondonia, AM = Amazonas, PA = Para.